

D6.4 Second Report on Communication and Dissemination Activities

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List of abbreviations

<Abbreviation>	<Explanation>
CAPS	Collective Awareness Platforms
CAPSSI	Collective Awareness Platforms for Sustainability and Social Innovation
COMRADES	Collective Platform for Community Resilience and Social Innovation during Crises
D5.3	D5.3 Second version of the COMRADES platform
D6.1	D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Action Plan
D6.3	D6.3 Initial Exploitation Plan
D6.4	D6.4 Second report on Communication and Dissemination Activities
D6.6	D6.6 Final Exploitation Plan
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
Gov2u	Government To You
HDX	Humanitarian Data Exchange
iHub	iHub Ltd
Mx	Month x
NGO	Non-Government Organization
OCHA	United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs
OU	Open University
Tx.y	Task x.y
TUD	Delft University
UIA	Universitetet i Agder
UN	United Nations
USFD	University of Sheffield
WP	Work Package
Yx	Year x

Executive summary

The current document under the title D6.4 “Second Report on Communication and Dissemination Activities” is a yearly report on the communication and dissemination activities implemented by the COMRADES project during its second year (*January 2017 – December 2017*). Particularly, it addresses two main aspects: a) the communication tools (*website, social media, e-newsletter, digital publishing platforms etc.*) that the consortium employed and the actions that were undertaken by using these tools within year 2, and b) the communication and dissemination activities performed such as workshops and conferences organized by the COMRADES, participation in third party events, media coverage, publications and so on.

D6.4 is a public deliverable of this project, part of the WP6, and consists of an update of D6.2 “First report on Communication and Dissemination activities” that was submitted to the European Commission in M12 (*December 2016*). Information concerning the project’s scope and objectives as well as WP6 is also presented in order to ensure that no prior knowledge related to the project, the Description of Action (DoA), and the other WP6 deliverables is requested from the reader. Overall, it is based on, and is consistent with, the DoA and the GA, but is not a substitute for reading these documents.

1 Introduction

1.1 The project: COMRADES

COMRADES project was launched in January 2016 with a lifetime of 36 months and it aims to empower communities with intelligent socio-technical solutions to help them reconnect, respond to, and recover from crisis situations.

COMRADES consortium is building a new generation, intelligent resilience platform to provide high socio-technical innovation and to support community resilience in crises situations. The platform will capture and process in real-time, multilingual social information streams from distributed communities, for the purpose of identifying, aggregating, and verifying reported events at the citizen and community levels. Resilience frameworks, guidelines and best practices will be embedded into the platform design and functionality, and enriched with open datasets and open source software.

The main objectives of the project are to foster social innovation during crises for safeguarding communities during critical scenarios from inaccurate, distrusted, and overhyped information, and for raising citizen and community awareness of crisis situations by providing them with filtered, validated, enriched, high quality and ad actionable knowledge. Community decision-making will be assisted by automated methods for real-time intelligent processing and linking of crowdsourced crisis information.

1.2 WP6 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication

This work package provides the overall coordination effort for dissemination and exploitation, and communicating the project to external parties. It will proactively plan, execute, and report all relevant activities, and ensure that COMRADES engages fully in collaborative events such as international conferences and builds appropriate partnerships with other CAPS projects, and will facilitate collaboration with external bodies in Europe and standards bodies.

There will be a particular focus on building the community of COMRADES researchers, and connecting with the developers and user communities of crises resilience platforms. WP6 will work with other work packages to ensure appropriate instrumentation and integration of all COMRADES developments within the evolving scholarly and practitioner communications ecosystem, reporting on these innovations and experiences in the activities in T6.2. WP6 objectives include:

- Establish and maintain mechanisms for effective and timely internal and external communication;
- Ensure the project achieves widest impact and effective exploitation of results through effective internal and external communications strategy;
- Identify methods and opportunities to ensure sustainability of the COMRADES output beyond the three year duration of the project;
- Communicate project achievements with external stakeholders, and with other CAPS projects in particular;
- Public facing activities including project website, social networks, event coordination.

2 D6.4 Second Report on Communication and Dissemination Activities

2.1 Scope of the deliverable

According to the DoA the scope of this deliverable is to provide a full report on the communication and dissemination activities implemented in the second year of the project. In particular, it presents to the reader the dissemination and communication objectives within the period M13-M24 and describes the tools used and activities performed for reaching them.

2.2 Intended audience

The intended audience of this deliverable is described in the table below:

<i>Intended audience</i>	<i>Reasons for interest in reading</i>
COMRADES project partners	To be informed about the dissemination activities during the reporting period.
European Commission	This is a deliverable of the COMRADES project and presents the progress made regarding dissemination and communication of the project in Y2 (<i>report</i>).
Target groups: <i>Activists / deployers, responders, individual citizens, civil society groups, humanitarian organisations and professional networks, scientific community and CAPS network, 11standardization bodies, media, think tanks and other experts</i>	To be informed on the communication and dissemination activities performed within the period M13-M24. Additionally, to be familiarized with the communication tools that were used by WP6 and visit, follow, connect, like, view etc. these tools.
Representatives of organizations involved into similar projects	To share knowledge, information and best practices that can be adopted and utilized in other similar projects, as well as to enhance their visibility via cross-dissemination of activities and events
Anyone interested	To share knowledge, information, lessons learnt during the implementation of the COMRADES project aiming to achieve visibility in wider audiences, raise awareness on the topics of disaster management, volunteerism and in general contributing to the communities' resilience.

Table 1 : Intended audience

2.3 Structure of the document

The D6.4 is comprised of seven chapters and three appendices. The first chapter introduces to the reader the COMRADES project, its objectives as well as a summary of the tasks and the objectives of WP6. The second chapter describes in brief the scope of the current deliverable, the audience that it is addressed to, the methodology followed for its creation and so on. The third one outlines the communication and dissemination objectives for Y2.

The fourth chapter presents the communication tools that the consortium employed and in parallel it delineates all the actions that were undertaken by using these tools within the same period. The fifth chapter gives all the information around the communication and dissemination activities made and highlights (*mostly via respective photos*) some of these activities. Chapter 4 and chapter 5 constitute the main part of the current document.

The sixth one serves as an overview of the reported activities and also as a description of the planned actions for Y3. Lastly, the conclusion summarizes the main points and issues presented in this deliverable.

2.4 Methodology followed

The creation of this deliverable was based on the close collaboration among the consortium for reporting efficiently the performed activities in Y2. Throughout this period each partner informed the WP6 leader for the developments on the topic. Bi-annually, they provided to Gov2u a consolidated report with these activities for ensuring the quality of the provided information. The initial draft version of the D6.4 “Second report on Communication and Dissemination activities” deliverable was produced after collecting all the reports. Later on, it was circulated via email communication to the consortium for reviewing and commenting. After incorporating all comments/suggestions, WP6 leader sent the final version to the project coordinator (*OU*) for submission to the European Commission.

2.5 Quality of the document

For ensuring the quality of the current document, online communication on the topic via emails and teleconferences was conducted. GOV2U, as WP6 leader, prepared the initial draft and distributed it to project partners for review and contribution. This deliverable uses the official template of the COMRADES project and language quality control has been performed.

2.6 Relation with other WP6 deliverables

This deliverable constitutes an update of the D6.2 “*First report on Communication and Dissemination activities*” of the current work page. However, it is also interrelated with the other WP6 deliverables. The table below explains the dependencies and relation of each one:

Title of WP6 Deliverable	Dependencies and relation with D6.4
D6.1 “ <i>Dissemination and Communication Action Plan</i> ” {M6}	Set the communication and dissemination strategy, identified groups and envisaged the tools to be used throughout the project’s duration.
D6.2 “ <i>First report on Communication and Dissemination activities</i> ”{M12}	Produced the report for the first year of project’s implementation concerning the dissemination activities that were carried out

	by the consortium. It also included the progress made related to the action plan and activities that are also described in this deliverable as well.
D6.3 <i>“Initial exploitation plan” {M18}</i>	It described the initial plan for the exploitation actions that will follow the upcoming period. Overall, it presented the strategy of the project as a business product and model in the relevant market, identifying the needed actions and target audiences to attract. The exploitation actions will be built upon the communication actions (WP6), innovation actions (WP5) and research actions to the extent of community engagement (WP2).
D6.5 <i>“Third report on communication and dissemination activities” {M36}</i>	It will produce the annual report of the third year of project’s implementation concerning the dissemination activities that will be carried out by the consortium. D6.5 will constitute an update of the current deliverable.
D6.6 <i>“Final exploitation plan”</i>	It will form an update of the deliverable D6.3 and will describe the final plan for exploiting the project’s outcomes. In other words, it will present the strategy of the project as a business product and model in the relevant market, identifying the needed actions and target audiences to attract. The exploitation actions will be built upon the communication actions (WP6), innovation actions (WP5) and research actions to the extent of community engagement (WP2).

Table 2 : Relation of D6.4 with other WP6 deliverables

3 Communication and Dissemination objectives for Y2

This chapter provides an overview of the dissemination and communication objectives for the second year of project's implementation (*January 2017 – December 2017*).

During this reporting period, WP6 focused its efforts on promoting the project's concept and objectives as well as its first outcomes at local, pan-European and international level. Moreover further expansion of the stakeholders' network and new contacts has been achieved. These activities were realized through various communication channels and dissemination activities.

The main objectives of WP6 for Y2 were the following:

- Maintain and regularly update the COMRADES website;
- Promote and distribute the promotional materials of the project (*project brochure, project factsheet and project poster*);
- Expand the stakeholders' network and establish new contacts;
- Exploit the social media accounts and other channels for delivering messages to different audience and engage them;
- Prepare, create, design and deliver the second newsletter issue;
- Participation in events at national, European and international level to raise the awareness and the visibility for the project;
- Communicate the project's results towards potentially interested parties across stakeholders;
- Organize events such workshops, conferences, lectures etc. for achieving greater engagement with the target groups;
- Establish, maintain and enhance collaboration with other EU funded projects in the same domain, especially with other CAPS projects;
- Investigate ways to exploit the project's results and foster the sustainability of the project after the end of the grant;
- Maintain and ensure the smooth internal communication among partners concerning the communication and dissemination activities of the project;
- Provide the deliverables and reports corresponding to the reporting period M12- M24

The chapters 4 and 5 that follow present in detail how the aforementioned objectives of the project for Y2 were met by the WP6 partners.

4 Communication tools and actions taken

This chapter provides to the reader a detail report about the communication tools that the consortium used during Y2 and in parallel it outlines all the actions that were taken by using these tools within the same period. Chapter 4 together with chapter 5 constitute the main part of the current document.

4.1 COMRADES website

The most important online communication channel, for all kinds of project, is the website. It plays a key role in transmitting the desired messages to target groups and ensures its presence in all available online search engines.

In this context, the COMRADES website was launched in M3 and since then it serves as the major mean of information for communication with the stakeholders. For this reason, several amendments/additions have been made during Y2 in order to ensure that it is harmonized and interrelated with the main goals of the WP6 which briefly are:

- promote the project’s concept and objectives;
- share the produced knowledge and ensure the widest visibility of these outcomes;
- communicate the COMRADES achievements with external stakeholders as well as with the other CAPS projects;
- engage the key stakeholders.

The aforementioned goals were covered by adding the sections “*Outputs*”, “*Press Kit*” and “*Related Projects*”. The “*Outputs*” section is consisted by the following three sub-sections: “*Deliverables*”, “*Papers*” and “*Datasets & Ontologies*”. As the project enters to a more mature phase, the produced outcomes are available to anyone who is interested in accessing them. Particularly, the public deliverables approved by the European Commission can be found at the “*Deliverables*” subsection (see **Figure 2**) while papers produced and presented by the consortium during Y1 and Y2 on “*Papers*” (see **Figure 3**). Additionally, under the framework of sharing the produced knowledge, the DoRES ontology as well as the data sets collected from crisis related tweets can be acquired at “*Datasets & Ontologies*” (see **Figure 4**).

Figure 1 : “Outputs” section

D6.4 Second Report on Communication and Dissemination Activities

Figure 2 : "Deliverables" subsection

Figure 3 : "Papers" subsection

Figure 4 : "Datasets & Ontologies" subsection

The tools that the consortium has used so far for communicating with wide audience have been clustered together at the section “*Press Kit*”. The information contained assist WP6 in achieving the goal of promoting to the general public and stakeholders the project’s concept, objectives and its latest developments.

The “*Press Kit*” section (see **Figure 5**) consists four subsections which namely are the following ones: “*Promotional Materials*”, “*Newsletter*”, “*Press Releases*” and “*Presentations*”. The promotional materials that have been created in Y1 and Y2 are freely accessible on “[Promotional Materials](#)” subsection (see **Figure 6**). All newsletter issues published so far can be easily found online via the COMRADES website at subsection “[Newsletter](#)” (see **Figure 7**).

Figure 5 : “Press Kit” section

Figure 6 : “Promotional materials” subsection

Figure 7 : “Newsletter” subsection

The overall presentation of the project can inform anyone interested about the COMRADES and its objectives in a quick manner and thus it is uploaded at “[Presentations](#)” subsection (see [Figure 9](#)). The updated overall presentation as well as other presentations of the project will populate this subsection.

Lastly, concerning the “[Press releases](#)” subsection (see [Figure 8](#)) will serve as a depository of the communication activities addressed to the press and assist the WP6 in further dissemination of project’s results.

Figure 8 : “Press releases” subsection

Figure 9 : “Presentations” subsection

WP6 aiming in expanding its network communicated with CAPS project and invited them to establish cross dissemination synergies. The outcome of this action led in the collaboration with 6 of them. For this reason the section [“Related Projects”](#) (see **Figure 10**) was added and it contains the descriptions, the logos and the websites of the CAPS projects that COMRADES cooperates with.

Figure 10 : “Related Projects” section

Overall, the project’s website has been regularly updated with news and developments around the COMRADES as well as news related to its topic. The content that has been used is easy-to-read in order to ensure that the information it contains can be comprehended by all audiences. This practice assists in growing the number of returning visitors and also attract new ones at the website. The measurement of the performance of the project’s website during the reporting period has been made by using the freemium web analytics service

named **Google Analytics**¹. The following table presents the data retrieved from this service and covers the period from 01/01/2017 to 04/12/2017 (*last measurement*). The respective figures can be found In **Appendix I**.

<i>COMRADES Website Performance in Y2</i>	
Users	1,482
Pageviews	17,443
Sessions	2,337
Number of New Visits	873 Sessions (37.4%)
Number of Returning Visits	1,464 Sessions (62.6%)
% New sessions	62.64%
Pages / Session	7.46
Avg. Session Duration	00:03:19
Bounce Rate	4.28

Table 3 : COMRADES Website performance in Y2

The explanation of the terms used for measuring the performance of the COMRADES website is provided below as it has been originally given by the Google Analytics service.

- **Users:** Users who have initiated at least one session during the date range. Learn more about how Analytics calculates the number of users.
- **Pageviews:** Pageviews is the total number of pages viewed. Repeated views of a single page are counted.
- **Sessions:** Total number of Sessions within the date range. A session is the period time a user is actively engaged with your website, app, etc. All usage data (*Screen Views, Events, Ecommerce, etc.*) is associated with a session.
- **% New Sessions:** An estimate of the percentage of first time visits
- **Avg. Session Duration:** The average length of a Session.
- **Bounce Rate:** The percentage of single-page sessions in which there was no interaction with the page. A bounced session has a duration of 0 seconds.

4.2 Newsletter

The newsletter is a communication tool that assists WP6 in reaching the target groups and conveying to them the major COMRADES developments with main aim to attract their attention and engage them. The newsletter issues are delivered via email (*e-newsletter*) and for this reason they are published corresponding to the internal activity frequency of the project, in order to avoid spamming target audiences with little content. For distributing (*via email*) the e-newsletter issues we use the free service of [Moosend](#). It is an email marketing

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Google_Analytics

service provider where its users can manage their mailing lists, craft their newsletters, schedule their delivery and track and evaluate their performance.

The period that we examine (*January 2017 – December 2017*) our project published one newsletter issue, which constitutes the second newsletter issue from the beginning of its lifetime.

The latest issue was published in June 2017 and as a main topic had the COMRADES workshops in Nepal. Nevertheless, information from other project's developments was not omitted. Particularly, the second newsletter issue had the structure (*sections*) as follows:

- **COMRADES Workshops in Nepal:** it serves as an editorial so the reader could be introduced with the performed actions in Nepal and informed about the workshops, focus group sessions, lectures, and interviews conducted within the 16 days stay of the project's partners in the area.
- **Stories:** this chapter presents briefly few stories that were occurred during partners' stay in Nepal.
- **Opinions:** presents the opinions of individuals who were involved with the COMRADES project.
- **Other project news:** informs the reader for other project's developments beyond the COMRADES activities in Nepal.
- **Events & conferences:** interesting events and conferences related to the project's topic.
- **Social Media & Contact:** gives information about how the reader can contact with the COMRADES project.

Figure 11 : 2nd Newsletter Issue – Editorial

Screenshots taken from the chapters of the second newsletter issue can be found in **Appendix III**. However, it is available [online](#) for reading at the project's website and all issues

are on “Press Kit”, subsection “[Newsletter](#)”. The third newsletter issue will be published in June 2018. Lastly, metrics received from Moosend and the back end of the COMRADES website are presented in **table 4**.

<i>Newsletter Issue No.2 -Analytics</i>	
Subscribers <i>(via project's website)</i>	47
Recipients	576
Unique opens	17.4% <i>(or 100 unique)</i>
Not open	81.1%
Link clicks	0.7% <i>(or 4 unique emails)</i>
Unsubscribe	1.7% <i>(or 10 recipients)</i>

Table 4 : Newsletter Issue No.2 - Analytics

4.3 COMRADES social media

Social media are powerful and significant tools for communication with a wider audience as through one source many recipients can be reached. For greater outreach and also taking advantage of the benefits that these means offer, accounts in Twitter, LinkedIn and a Facebook page were created from the very start of the project.

4.3.1 Facebook page

Facebook is an online social media and social networking service. After registering to use the site, users can create a user profile indicating their name, occupation, schools attended and so on. Users can add other users as "friends", exchange messages, post status updates and digital photos, share digital videos and links, use various software applications ("*apps*"), and receive notifications when others update their profiles or make posts. ²

Figure 12 : COMRADES Facebook Page

² Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Facebook> (Wikipedia)

The Facebook page of the COMRADES project was created in January 2016 (M1) and since then it has been regularly updated with project news, interesting events and relevant information such as news from the CAPs projects. According to the latest measurement on 4th December 2017 the number of page likes was 138. In comparison with the previous measurement in December 2016 the number of page likes has been increased in 272.97% or 101 new likes in Y2.

Facebook Page	
Created in (Project Month)	January 2016 (M1)
URL	https://www.facebook.com/comradesproject/
Mention	@comradesproject
Number of Page Likes Y1 (Previous Measurement)	37 Likes (December 2016)
Number of Page Likes Y2 (Last Measurement)	138 Likes (December 2017)
% Page Likes increase / decrease in Y2 ($\frac{Y2-Y1}{Y1} \times 100$)	272.97% increase

Table 5 : Current status of the Facebook Page

Figure 13 : Likes growth - Facebook

4.3.2 Twitter profile

Twitter is an online news and social networking service where users post and interact with messages, "tweets", restricted to 140 characters. Registered users can post tweets, but those who are unregistered can only read them.³

Figure 14 : COMRADES Twitter profile

The Twitter profile of the COMRADES project was created in January 2016 (M1) and since then it has been regularly updated with project news, interesting events and relevant information such as news from the CAPs projects. According to the latest measurement on the 4th December 2017 the number of followers was 309. In comparison with the previous measurement in December 2016 the number of followers has been increased in 41.09% or 90 new followers in Y2.

Twitter Profile	
Created in (Project Month)	January 2016 (M1)
URL	https://twitter.com/comradesproject
Mention	@comradesproject
Number of Page Followers Y1 (Previous Measurement)	219 Followers (December 2016)
Number of Page Followers Y2 (Last Measurement)	309 Followers (December 2017)
% Followers increase / decrease in Y2 ($\frac{Y2-Y1}{Y1} \times 100$)	41.09% increase

Table 6 : Current status of the Twitter profile

³ Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Twitter> (Wikipedia)

Figure 15 : Followers growth - Twitter

Figure 16 : Tweet impressions in Y2 - Twitter

Figure 17 : Profile visits in Y2 – Twitter

4.3.3 LinkedIn profile

LinkedIn is a business-and employment-oriented social networking service that operates via websites and mobile apps. It is mainly used for professional networking, including employers posting jobs and job seekers posting their CVs. LinkedIn allows members (*both workers and employers*) to create profiles and "connections" to each other in an online social network which may represent real-world professional relationships. Members can invite anyone (*whether an existing member or not*) to become a connection. The "gated-access approach" (*where contact with any professional requires either an existing relationship or an introduction through a contact of theirs*) is intended to build trust among the service's members.⁴

Figure 18 : COMRADES LinkedIn profile

⁴ Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/LinkedIn> (Wikipedia)

The LinkedIn profile of the COMRADES project was created in January 2016 (M1) and since then it has been regularly updated with project news, interesting events and relevant information such as news from the CAPs projects.

According to the latest measurement on the 4th December 2017 the number of connections was 123. In comparison with the previous measurement in December 2016 the number of followers has been increased in 80.88% or 55 new connections in Y2.

<i>LinkedIn Profile</i>	
Created in <i>(Project Month)</i>	January 2016 <i>(M1)</i>
URL	https://www.linkedin.com/in/comradesproject/
Number of Page Likes Y1 <i>(Previous Measurement)</i>	68 Connections <i>(December 2016)</i>
Number of Page Likes Y2 <i>(Last Measurement)</i>	123 Connections <i>(December 2017)</i>
% Connections increase / decrease in Y2 <i>($\{Y2-Y1\}/Y1 \times 100$)</i>	80.88% increase

Table 7 : Current status of the LinkedIn profile

Figure 19 : Connections growth – LinkedIn

4.4 Digital Publishing Platforms

Electronic publishing⁵ (also referred to as *e-publishing* or *digital publishing* or *online publishing*) includes the digital publication of e-books, digital magazines, and the development of digital libraries and catalogues.

In COMRADES we have used three different platforms (*Issuu, Scribd, LinkedIn Slideshare*) for digital publishing that served as tools of dissemination for promoting the outcomes of the project such as public deliverables (*approved by EC*), papers (*publications*) and promotional materials (*e.g. poster, newsletter issues, etc.*).

4.4.1 Issuu profile

Issuu is a free electronic publishing platform for magazines, catalogs, and newspapers.⁶ The profile of COMRADES on Issuu was created in June 2017 (*M18*) and can be found at:

<https://issuu.com/comradeseuproject>

The screenshot shows the Issuu profile for 'COMRADES EU Project'. The profile features a red 'A' logo and an 'EDIT PROFILE' button. The main text describes the project as an open-source, community resilience platform designed by communities for communities. It mentions funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 687847. Below the profile, there are two tabs: 'PUBLICATIONS (22)' and 'STACKS (0)'. The 'PUBLICATIONS' tab is active, showing a grid of four publication thumbnails. Each thumbnail includes a title, a small image, and the text 'COMRADES EU Project'.

Figure 20 : COMRADES Issuu profile

The platform provides some free statistics concerning the overall performance of the profile as well as per published item.

⁵ Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Electronic_publishing (Wikipedia)

⁶ Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Issuu> (Wikipedia)

Lifetime Statistics for **COMRADES EU Project**

You have been a member since June 23rd 2017

Figure 21 : COMRADES Issuu profile overall performance

The explanation of the metrics terms (as given by Issuu) that are showcased in **Figure 21** is:

- **Reads:** Counted each time a user opened a publication for more than 2 seconds.
- **Impressions:** Counted each time a publication was displayed to a user in an embedded or on Issuu.
- **Followers:** The number of users following your Issuu profile.
- **Likes:** The number of users following your Issuu profile.
- **Shares:** The number of times a user shared your publication from Issuu.
- **Link-outs:** Number of clicks on a publisher made link.
- **Average time spent:** The average time readers spent reading this publication
- **Read time:** The total time readers spend reading this publication

Figure 22 : Readers around the world

The list with the published items on COMRADES Issuu profile is presented in the table below.

S/N	Title of the published item	URL	Type	Reads	Impressions	Average time spend	Read time
1.	COMRADES EU Project Factsheet	https://issuu.com/comradeseuproject/docs/comrades_eu_project_factsheet	Marketing material	12	37	0:03:21	0:40:13
2.	COMRADES EU Project Overall Presentation	https://issuu.com/comradeseuproject/docs/comrades_eu_project_overall_presentation	Marketing material	3	21	0:13:06	0:39:20
3.	COMRADES EU Project Brochure	https://issuu.com/comradeseuproject/docs/comrades_eu_project_brochure	Marketing material	3	24	0:00:13	0:00:41
4.	COMRADES EU Project Poster	https://issuu.com/comradeseuproject/docs/comrades_poster_2017_web	Marketing material	6	24	0:00:33	0:03:20
5.	COMRADES EU Project Newsletter Issue No.1 - July 2016	https://issuu.com/comradeseuproject/docs/comrades_newsletter_no.1	Newsletter Issue	4	40	0:00:54	0:03:37
6.	COMRADES EU Project Newsletter Issue No.2 - June 2017	https://issuu.com/comradeseuproject/docs/comrades_newsletter_no.2	Newsletter Issue	4	34	0:00:45	0:03:00
7.	D2.1 Requirements for boosting community resilience in crisis situation	https://issuu.com/comradeseuproject/docs/comrades_d2.1_final	Public Deliverable	4	33	0:00:53	0:03:32
8.	D2.2 Socio-Technical Community	https://issuu.com/comradeseuproject/docs/comrades_d2.2_socio-technical_community	Public Deliverable	2	22	0:00:22	0:00:44

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	Requirements	rades_d2.2_final					
9.	D2.3 Community Based Evaluation	https://issuu.com/comradeseuproject/docs/d2.3-final	Public Deliverable	2	22	0:00:27	0:00:55
10.	D3.1 Multilingual content processing methods	https://issuu.com/comradeseuproject/docs/d3.1	Public Deliverable	2	16	0:00:12	0:00:24
11.	D4.1 Enriched Semantic Models of Emergency Events	https://issuu.com/comradeseuproject/docs/comrades_d4.1v6	Public Deliverable	6	28	0:01:57	0:11:42
12.	D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Action Plan	https://issuu.com/comradeseuproject/docs/d6.1_dissemination_and_communication	Public Deliverable	2	27	0:00:10	0:00:20
13.	D6.2 First report on Communication and Dissemination activities	https://issuu.com/comradeseuproject/docs/d6.2_first_report_on_dissemination	Public Deliverable	2	15	0:01:19	0:02:39
14.	DoRES — A Three-tier Ontology for Modelling Crises in the Digital Age	https://issuu.com/comradeseuproject/docs/dores	Conf. paper	2	15	0:05:00	0:10:00
15.	On Semantics and Deep Learning for Event Detection in Crisis Situations	https://issuu.com/comradeseuproject/docs/event_detection	Workshop paper	1	18	0:00:35	0:00:35

16.	Detecting Important Life Events on Twitter Using Frequent Semantic and Syntactic Subgraphs	https://issuu.com/comradeseuproject/docs/detecting-important-life-events-on	Journal paper	1	4	0:00:23	0:00:23
17.	Prospecting Socially-Aware Concepts and Artefacts for Designing for Community Resilience	https://issuu.com/comradeseuproject/docs/prospecting-socially-aware	Workshop paper	1	4	0:00:23	0:00:23
18.	Behind the Scenes of Scenario-Based Training: Understanding Scenario Design and Requirements in High	https://issuu.com/comradeseuproject/docs/1525-nadiasaadnoori-et-al2017	Conf. paper	2	31	0:02:55	0:05:50
19.	SemEval-2017 Task 8: RumourEval: Determining rumour veracity and support for rumours	https://issuu.com/comradeseuproject/docs/rumoureval-task	Workshop paper	1	7	0:01:17	0:01:17
20.	Sustainable Performance Measurement for Humanitari	https://issuu.com/comradeseuproject/docs/1510-lauralaqunaslavado-et-al2017	Conf. paper	3	7	0:04:01	0:12:05

	an Supply Chain Operations						
21.	Designing for Networked Community Resilience	https://issuu.com/comradeseuproject/docs/humtech2016_comes_1	Conf. paper	2	27	0:00:17	0:00:35
22.	A Semantic Graph-based Approach for Radicalisation Detection on Social Media	https://issuu.com/comradeseuproject/docs/radicalisation_detection	Conf. paper	1	6	0:06:40	0:06:40

Table 8 : List of published items & metrics – Issuu profile

4.4.2 Scribd profile

Scribd is a digital library, e-book and audiobook subscription service.⁷ The profile of COMRADES on SCRIBD was created in June 2017 (M18) and can be found at:

<https://www.scribd.com/user/362001050/COMRADES-EU-Project>

Figure 23 : COMRADES Scribd profile

On Scribd profile of the COMRADES we have uploaded 22 items (*deliverables, papers, promotional materials*) that are free accessible to anyone interested reading and/or downloading them. The table below presents all items published as well as analytics (*views*).

⁷ Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Scribd> (Wikipedia)

S/N	Title of published item	URL	Type	Total Views
1.	COMRADES EU Project Factsheet	https://www.scribd.com/document/352068989/COMRAD-ES-EU-Project-Factsheet	Promotional material	4
2.	COMRADES EU Project Overall Presentation	https://www.scribd.com/document/352069105/COMRAD-ES-EU-Project-Overall-Presentation	Promotional material	4
3.	COMRADES EU Project Brochure	https://www.scribd.com/document/352069254/COMRAD-ES-EU-Project-Brochure	Promotional material	2
4.	COMRADES EU Project Poster	https://www.scribd.com/document/365178086/COMRAD-ES-EU-Project-Poster	Promotional material	7
5.	COMRADES EU Project Newsletter Issue No.1 - July 2016	https://www.scribd.com/document/365190198/COMRAD-ES-EU-Project-Newsletter-Issue-No-1-July-2016	Newsletter Issue	4
6.	COMRADES EU Project Newsletter Issue No.2 - June 2017	https://www.scribd.com/document/365190353/COMRAD-ES-EU-Project-Newsletter-Issue-No-2-June-2017	Newsletter Issue	4
7.	D2.1 Requirements for boosting community resilience in crisis situation	https://www.scribd.com/document/365285824/D2-1-Requirements-for-boosting-community-resilience-in-crisis-situation	Public Deliverable	3
8.	D2.2 Socio-Technical Community Requirements	https://www.scribd.com/document/365289138/D2-2-Socio-Technical-Community-Requirements	Public Deliverable	4
9.	D2.3 Community Based Evaluation	https://www.scribd.com/document/365288905/d2-3-community-based-evaluation	Public Deliverable	3
10.	D3.1 Multilingual content processing methods	https://www.scribd.com/document/365289774/D3-1-Multilingual-content-processing-methods	Public Deliverable	4
11.	D4.1 Enriched Semantic Models of Emergency Events	https://www.scribd.com/document/365291945/d4-1-enriched-semantic-models-of-emergency-events	Public Deliverable	3

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12.	D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Action Plan	https://www.scribd.com/document/365292235/D6-1-Dissemination-and-Communication-Action-Plan	Public Deliverable	4
13.	D6.2 First report on Communication and Dissemination activities	https://www.scribd.com/document/365292391/D6-2-First-report-on-Communication-and-Dissemination-activities	Public Deliverable	2
14.	DoRES — A Three-tier Ontology for Modelling Crises in the Digital Age	https://www.scribd.com/document/365364886/DoRES-A-Three-tier-Ontology-for-Modelling-Crises-in-the-Digital-Age	Conf. paper	3
15.	On Semantics and Deep Learning for Event Detection in Crisis Situations	https://www.scribd.com/document/365374554/On-Semantics-and-Deep-Learning-for-Event-Detection-in-Crisis-Situations	Workshop paper	5
16.	Detecting Important Life Events on Twitter Using Frequent Semantic and Syntactic Subgraphs	https://www.scribd.com/document/365370531/Detecting-Important-Life-Events-on-Twitter-Using-Frequent-Semantic-and-Syntactic-Subgraphs	Journal paper	7
17.	Prospecting Socially-Aware Concepts and Artefacts for Designing for Community Resilience	https://www.scribd.com/document/365375000/Prospecting-Socially-Aware-Concepts-and-Artefacts-for-Designing-for-Community-Resilience	Workshop paper	5
18.	Behind the Scenes of Scenario-Based Training: Understanding Scenario Design and Requirements in High	https://www.scribd.com/document/365374043/Behind-the-Scenes-of-Scenario-Based-Training-Understanding-Scenario-Design-and-Requirements-in-High-Risk-and-Uncertain-Environments	Conf. paper	5
19.	SemEval-2017 Task 8: RumourEval: Determining rumour veracity and support for rumours	https://www.scribd.com/document/365375332/SemEval-2017-Task-8-RumourEval-Determining-rumour-veracity-and-support-for-rumours	Workshop paper	3
20.	Sustainable Performance Measurement for	https://www.scribd.com/document/365373421/Sustainab	Conf. paper	6

	Humanitarian Supply Chain Operations	le-Performance-Measurement-for-Humanitarian-Supply-Chain-Operations		
21.	Designing for Networked Community Resilience	https://www.scribd.com/document/365376636/Designing-for-Networked-Community-Resilience	Conf. paper	3
22.	A Semantic Graph-based Approach for Radicalisation Detection on Social Media	https://www.scribd.com/document/365374244/A-Semantic-Graph-based-Approach-for-Radicalisation-Detection-on-Social-Media	Conf. paper	3

Table 9 : List of published items & metrics – Scribd profile

4.4.3 LinkedIn Slideshare account

LinkedIn SlideShare is a Web 2.0–based slide hosting service where users can upload files privately or publicly in the following file formats: PowerPoint, PDF, Keynote or OpenDocument presentations. Slide decks can then be viewed on the site itself, on hand held devices or embedded on other sites. Although the website is primarily a slide hosting service, it also supports documents, PDFs, videos and webinars. It also provides to the users the ability to rate, comment on, and share the uploaded content.⁸

The account of COMRADES on Slideshare was created in June 2017 (M18) and can be found at: <https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject>

Figure 24 : COMRADES Slideshare account

The analytics of the COMRADES account are provided by the LinkedIn Slideshare and are presented below (see figures 25, 26, 27, 28).

⁸ Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/SlideShare> (Wikipedia)

Figure 25 : Summary of the COMRADES Slideshare account

Top content

Name	Views
D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Action Plan	61
A Semantic Graph-based Approach for Radicalisation Detection on Social Media	36
Detecting Important Life Events on Twitter Using Frequent Semantic and Syntactic Subgraphs	35
COMRADES EU Project Newsletter Issue No.1 - July 2016	28
COMRADES EU Project Overall Presentation	22

Figure 26 : Top content - Slideshare account

Top countries

Name	Views
Greece	196
Japan	51
France	44
United States	39
Canada	7

Figure 27 : Top countries - Slideshare account

Figure 28 : Traffic sources - Slideshare account

The following table presents all items published as well as analytics (*total views*).

S/N	Title of published item	URL	Type	Total Views
1.	COMRADES EU Project Factsheet	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/comrades-eu-project-factsheet	Promotional material	10
2.	COMRADES EU Project Overall Presentation	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/comrades-eu-project-overall-presentation	Promotional material	22
3.	COMRADES EU Project Brochure	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/comrades-eu-project-brochure	Promotional material	13
4.	COMRADES EU Project Poster	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/comrades-eu-project-poster	Promotional material	9
5.	COMRADES EU Project Newsletter Issue No.1 - July 2016	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/comrades-eu-project-newsletter-issue-no1-july-2016	Newsletter Issue	28
6.	COMRADES EU Project Newsletter Issue No.2 - June 2017	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/comrades-eu-project-newsletter-issue-no2-june-2017	Newsletter Issue	16
7.	D2.1 Requirements for boosting community resilience in crisis situation	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/d21-requirements-for-boosting-community-resilience-in-crisis-situation	Public Deliverable	12

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8.	D3.1 Multilingual content processing methods	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/d31-multilingual-content-processing-methods	Public Deliverable	15
9.	D4.1 Enriched Semantic Models of Emergency Events	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/d41-enriched-semantic-models-of-emergency-events	Public Deliverable	11
10.	D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Action Plan	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/d61-dissemination-and-communication-action-plan	Public Deliverable	62
11.	D6.2 First report on Communication and Dissemination activities	https://www.slideshare.net/secret/88Aqa0ZNxEkky	Public Deliverable	13
12.	DoRES — A Three-tier Ontology for Modelling Crises in the Digital Age	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/does-a-threetier-ontology-for-modelling-crises-in-the-digital-age-82646499	Conf. paper	10
13.	On Semantics and Deep Learning for Event Detection in Crisis Situations	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/on-semantics-and-deep-learning-for-event-detection-in-crisis-situations	Workshop paper	20
14.	Detecting Important Life Events on Twitter Using Frequent Semantic and Syntactic Subgraphs	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/detecting-important-life-events-on-twitter-using-frequent-semantic-and-syntactic-subgraphs	Journal paper	35
15.	Prospecting Socially-Aware Concepts and Artefacts for Designing for Community Resilience	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/prospectinq-sociallyaware-concepts-and-artefacts-for-designing-for-community-resilience	Workshop paper	11
16.	Behind the Scenes of Scenario-Based Training: Understanding Scenario Design and Requirements in High	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/behind-the-scenes-of-scenariobased-training-understanding-scenario-design-and-requirements-in-highrisk-and-uncertain-environments	Conf. paper	9
17.	SemEval-2017 Task 8: RumourEval:	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/semEval2	Workshop	12

	Determining rumour veracity and support for rumours	017-task-8-rumoureval-determining-rumour-veracity-and-support-for-rumours	<i>paper</i>	
18.	Sustainable Performance Measurement for Humanitarian Supply Chain Operations	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/sustainable-performance-measurement-for-humanitarian-supply-chain-operations	<i>Conf. paper</i>	5
19.	Designing for Networked Community Resilience	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/designing-for-networked-community-resilience-82655928	<i>Conf. paper</i>	12
20.	A Semantic Graph-based Approach for Radicalisation Detection on Social Media	https://www.slideshare.net/COMRADESproject/a-semantic-graphbased-approach-for-radicalisation-detection-on-social-media-82654394	<i>Conf. paper</i>	36

Table 10 : List of published items & metrics – Slideshare

4.5 Promotional Materials

Marketing collaterals (*i.e. brochure, poster, factsheet*) are a collection of dissemination and promotional tools used to support the project’s identity widely, to raise awareness and visibility of the project, to attract and motivate stakeholders to get engaged to the project, as well as to be distributed to audiences during the project’s presentation in events, workshops and conferences.

In Y2, the COMRADES poster was prepared, designed and created aiming to assist the consortium in the communication activities such as the workshops and the other events that were organized within this period. Moreover, the brochure and the factsheet were updated with the addition of the [CAPSSI](#) logo.

In Y3, WP6 will update all promotional materials (*content and design*) with the scope in assisting also in exploitation activities that will be followed after the end of the EU funding as presented in the deliverable D6.3 “Initial Exploitation Plan”.

The promotional materials of the project are also available in digital format at project’s website on section “Press Kit”, subsection “[Promotional Materials](#)”. Moreover, for making the best out of the communication channels that we use in WP6, the materials have been uploaded on the COMRADES profiles at the digital publishing platforms *i.e.* Issuu, Scribd and Slideshare.

Screenshots of the project’s poster as well as the updated version of the factsheet and the brochure can be found in **Appendix II**.

5 Communication and Dissemination Activities

The current chapter includes all the information around the communication and dissemination activities performed in Y2. For readers ease, this information is presented via tables. Chapter 5 together with chapter 4 constitutes the main part of the current document.

5.1 Organization of events

In 5.1 the reader can find in detail all the events that were organized by the COMRADES consortium during the reporting period. These events had major contribution in the offline dissemination of the project due to the fact that they attracted attention and expanded its network in stakeholders, citizens, media, policy makers etc. and also provided valuable feedback to the project for its upcoming activities in Y3.

5.1.1 List of the COMRADES events

<i>S/N</i>	<i>Partner</i>	<i>Name of the event</i>	<i>Date of the event</i>	<i>Location of the event</i>	<i>Description of the event</i>
1.	OU	The Web Conf	23-27 Apr 2018	Lyon, France	Track on content analysis and semantics. 250 submissions. Audience is around 300 people (<i>academics, industry</i>)
2.	USFD	RumourEval	3 August 2017	Vancouver, Canada	Shared task where technical participants from around the world tried to gauge content veracity (<i>WP3</i>)
3.	USFD	WNUT	7 September 2017	Copenhagen, Denmark	Shared task on trying to detect emerging entities, used for identifying crisis locations and organisations
4.	TUD, Ushahidi	Focus group Discussion with School teachers of	27 January 2017	Palanchowk, Nepal	Share our initial findings and ideas, contacts

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		Shree Bhagwati Secondary school			and knowledge. Served as exploration of the role of information and technology to strengthen communities in Nepal.
5.	TUD, Ushahidi	Focus group Discussion with School teachers of Koshi Dehka School & Shree Palanchowk Bhagtwati Higher Secondary School	27 January 2017	Palanchowk, Nepal	Share our initial findings and ideas, contacts and knowledge. Served as exploration of the role of information and technology to strengthen communities in Nepal.
6.	TUD, Ushahidi	Workshop Cordair (VDC Secretary/Locals/District Management Committee) 25 participants	29 January 2017	Rasuwa, Nepal	Share our initial findings and ideas, contacts and knowledge. Served as exploration of the role of information and technology to strengthen communities in Nepal.
7.	TUD, Ushahidi	Workshop with District Disaster Management (GIZ/RPN, UNICEF, WFP, Save the children, ACF, OXFAM, Red cross, World Renew, DDRC,)	30 January 2017	Nuwakot, Nepal	Share our initial findings and ideas, contacts and knowledge. Served as exploration of the role of information and technology to strengthen communities in Nepal.
8.	TUD,	COMRADES conference -	1 February	KTM	Providing a forum to share

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	Ushahidi	Opening Ceremony by Senior Government Official (<i>Prime Minister or Home Minister</i>)			the initial results and exchange knowledge about the role of information in disasters.
9.	TUD, Ushahidi	Workshop at ICMS (<i>100 participants</i>)	1 February 2017	ICMS	Share our initial findings and ideas, contacts and knowledge. Served as exploration of the role of information and technology to strengthen communities in Nepal.
10.	TUD, Ushahidi	Workshop at ICMS (<i>100 participants</i>)	2 February 2017	ICMS	Share our initial findings and ideas, contacts and knowledge. Served as exploration of the role of information and technology to strengthen communities in Nepal.
11.	TUD	Summer School: Managing Flood Disasters in Delta Cities	18-24 June 2017	Beijing, China	Provided several lectures on community engagement and information management during the summer school. Attended by 40 students, 10 academics.
12.	TUD	Guest lecture at Institute for Disaster Prevention	15 June 2017	Beijing, China	Provided guest lecture, and conducted evaluation sessions with 10

					students (<i>trained professionals</i>) and 5 staff (<i>WP2</i>).
13.	TUD	Harvey Hackathon	13 September 2017	Delft Science Center, Netherlands	Twitter feed and satellite data analysis, to comparing the Harvey disaster to previous disasters. TU Delft presented what is already doing in this field.
14.	TUD	Evaluation 2 in MSc course “Design of Participatory Systems”	23 November, 30 November; 4 December 2017	Delft, Netherlands	Provided lecture on COMRADES, information management in distributed settings and conducted evaluation sessions attended by 11 MSc students (<i>WP2</i>)

Table 11 : List of the COMRADES events

5.1.2 Highlights from the COMRADES events

From the 18th of January to the 2nd of February 2017 the COMRADES consortium in close collaboration with the Institute of Crisis Management Studies (*ICMS*) of Tribhuvan University (Nepal) completed a series of highly successful international workshops. Over the course of 16 days, workshops, focus group sessions, lectures, and interviews with approximately 150 people in Kathmandu and in remote areas of Nepal were conducted.

At the end of the field visit a conference was organized, providing a forum to share the initial results and moreover for exchanging knowledge about the role of information in disasters. Attendees presented current and ongoing research, case studies from the field, and examined current research trends and methods. The conference helped to establish and strengthen networks of governmental officials, academic researchers, and members of the international community who share commitment to building resilience to disasters and specifically empowering local communities through information exchange.

A unique aspect was the inclusion of a wide variety of stakeholders from all political parties, representatives from front-line non-governmental organizations, and ICMS students who represent the future of Nepal.

Figure 29 : COMRADES Conference in Nepal – participants

Figure 30 : COMRADES Conference in Nepal – speakers' panel

Figure 31 : COMRADES Conference in Nepal –attended by the PM of Nepal

The COMRADES conference in Nepal was attended by the Prime Minister of the country (see **Figure 31**) and expressed his readiness to promote and implement risk reduction actions, as mentioned in the Sendai framework.

Figure 32 : COMRADES Conference in Nepal – Nepalese Minister of Industry presents the participation certificate

Throughout our field visits it is not only us who connected with the people of Nepal, but we also encouraged others to reach out and discuss how information supports resilient communities. Staff from local and international NGOs, politicians, academics, business owners, students and community leaders joined the COMRADES conversation during and after our field work. Here the Nepalese Minister of Industry - *Nabindra Raj Joshi* – presents the participation certificate to the Japanese chargé d'affaires. A few of the many dignitaries attending the COMRADES conference at the conclusion of the field work.

Figure 33 : COMRADES Workshop in Nepal

Figure 34 : COMRADES focus group session in Nepal

Figure 35 : COMRADES workshop in Rasuwa, Nepal

Figure 36 : COMRADES lecture in Nepal

A key element of the COMRADES project is to empower local communities. We not only design systems, processes and platform that support these communities, but we actively involve in the design process. Thanks to the NGO Cordaid, we managed to invite people from the Laharepauwa community, located in the Rasuwa district (*north of Kathmandu*) to a workshop. In **Figure 34**, they are mapping out what information was needed and available to them at various moment following the devastating 2015 earthquake. The results help us determine what information, when and through what channel supports the community in their decisions.

Figure 37 : COMRADES / ICMS symposium

Over the two and a half weeks, the field team, comprised of ICMS students, Cordaid staff and COMRADES researchers engaged with many different stakeholders. At the conclusion of the field visit a symposium was organised to share our initial findings. But more than the end, by sharing ideas, contacts and knowledge, it served as the start of further exploration of the role of information and technology to strengthen communities in Nepal.

Figure 38 : COMRADES / ICMS symposium – PM of Nepal hands out certificates

In the figure above the Prime Minister of Nepal - *Pushpa Kamal Dahal* - hands out certificates of appreciation to some of the dignitaries attending the workshop.

Beyond of the many activities made in Nepal, the project partners within Y2 were also very active in organizing events across the globe for promoting the COMRADES results. One of these events (*lecture in Beijing*) is depicted in **figure 39**.

Figure 39 : COMRADES lecture in Beijing, China

5.2 Participation in third party events

5.2.1 List of the COMRADES participation in third party events

S/N	Partner	Name of the event	Date of the event	Location of the event	Description of the event
1.	OU (<i>Harith Alani, Gregoire Burel, Miriam Fernandez</i>)	Int. Semantic Web Conf. (<i>ISWC</i>)	21 - 25 October, 2017	Vienna, Austria	Flagship Semantic Web conference. Around 700 attendees (academics, industry)
2.	OU (<i>Harith Alani</i>)	Int. Conf. on Weblogs and Social Media (<i>ICWSM</i>)	15 - 18 May, 2017	Montreal, Canada	Workshop on Digital Misinformation
3.	USFD	Grantham Centre for Sustainable Futures Annual Symposium	23 October, 2017	Sheffield, UK	Annual event showcasing multidisciplinary sustainability research across every Faculty of the University of Sheffield, with the theme this year FEWER – Food, Energy, Water and

					Environmental Research. Opportunities for networking, showcasing and discussing with Grantham Scholars and Supervisors. Academics, researchers, research-related staff and postgraduate students; Also external invited speakers.
4.	USFD	ESSENCE Conference on Computational Approaches to Diversity	7 - 9 October, 2017	San Servolo, Italy	Gave a presentation about social media analysis problems and solutions. Conference involved multidisciplinary AI research capitalizing on advances in technologies bridging diverse conceptualisations of knowledge through interaction. Participants were around 50 with a mix of disciplines.
5.	USFD	Big Data and Analytics Summer School	31 July - 1 August, 2017	University of Essex, UK	Presented a 2-day tutorial on social media analysis techniques including a COMRADES case study at the annual summer school. Audience were a mix of students, researchers and industrials. Around 30 participants in the tutorial; around 200 participants in the summer school.
6.	USFD	BCS Search Solutions	28 November,	London, UK	Presentation of a half-day tutorial at the

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		Tutorial	2017		Annual BCS conference involving around 50 participants and a mix of academic researchers and industrials, focused on Information Retrieval and Semantic Search. Includes a case study of COMRADES tools presented.
7.	USFD	ACL conference	30 July - 4 August, 2017	Vancouver, Canada	Academic conference of about 2000 industry members, scientists, linguists. Presenting results of RumourEval task and building links with crowdsourcing platform providers
8.	USFD	EMNLP conference	7 - 11 September, 2017	Copenhagen, Denmark	Academic conference with about 1600 scientists and industry members, working in AI and language processing; presented results of entity detection and extraction for parsing crisis-relevant messages
9.	USFD	RANLP conference	4 - 6 September, 2017	Varna, Bulgaria	Presenting state-of-the-art work on stance to 300 researchers, support WP3's content validity work
10.	USFD	RANLP conference	4 - 6 September, 2017	Varna, Bulgaria	Presenting multi-lingual open source lemmatizer to 200 researchers, support for feature extraction for WP3's stance work

11.	Gov2u	51 st ICA International conference	11 - 14 September, 2017	Tokyo, Japan	The Conference themed Bold Digital Government-dealing with disruptive technologies attended by governmental CIOs local stakeholders and national ministerial representatives
12.	USFD	Submitted ECIR conference	26 - 29 March, 2018	Grenoble, France	Once it is accepted, we will present rumour verification work using stance only.
13.	USFD	European Semantic Web Conference	28 May – 1 June, 2017	Portoroz, Slovenia	Programme Co-chair of one of the biggest Semantic Web conferences; around 300 participants from academia & industry

Table 12 : List of the COMRADES participation in third party events

5.2.2 Highlights from the COMRADES participation in third party events

The COMRADES project was discussed among Breakout Group 4 during Sessions VI and VII on Interaction Day of the [51st ICA International Conference](#) which took place in Tokyo, Japan September 11th-14th. WP6 leader attended the conference and discussed the abilities of COMRADES during discussions addressing the topic of misinformation and dealing with Disaster Management situations. The Conference themed Bold Digital Government-dealing with disruptive technologies was attended by international governmental CIOs from a number of countries from around the world as well as local stakeholders and national ministerial representatives.

Figure 40 : COMRADES presented in 51st ICA International Conference - Session VI

Figure 41 : COMRADES presented in 51st ICA International Conference - Session VII

5.3 Collaboration with other projects & initiatives

In Y2 the project entered in a more mature phase and its first outcomes were already available to be shared and communicated to stakeholders and general public. In this context for enhancing the dissemination activities of the project we contacted, invited and established collaborations with other EU funded projects and initiatives.

5.3.1 List of the established collaborations

S/N	Partner	Project's Name	Contact person & organization	Date	Description (collaboration activity)
1.	OU	ChiC	Organization: T6 Ecosystems Contact person: Dr. Antonella Passani,	July and November 2017	Gathering information about CAPS projects activities
2.	Gov2u	ASSET (CAPS project)	Organization: Verein für Konsumenteninformation Contact person: James Cora	Started in April 2017	Cross dissemination synergy
3.	Gov2u	CAPSELLA (CAPS project)	Organization: Zephyr srl Contact person: Giovanna Calabro	Started in April 2017	Cross dissemination synergy
4.	Gov2u	hackAIR (CAPS project)	Organization: ON:SUBJECT Contact person:	Started in April 2017	Cross dissemination synergy

			Wiebke Herding		
5.	Gov2u	Empatia (CAPS project)	Organization: University of Coimbra Contact person: Michelangelo Secchi	Started in April 2017	Cross dissemination synergy
6.	Gov2u	SavingFood (CAPS project)	Organization: ViLabs Contact person: Vasia Madesi	Started in May 2017	Cross dissemination synergy
7.	Gov2u	POWER (CAPS project)	Organization: Klima-Bündnis Contact person: Christiane Thomas	Started in October 2017	Cross dissemination synergy
8.	Gov2u	EDI-Net	Organization: Klima-Bündnis Contact person: Christiane Thomas	Started in October 2017	Cross dissemination synergy
9.	Ushahidi	Uchaguzi	Organization: Ushahidi Contact person: n/a	Started in June 2017	Uchaguzi Partnership, through Ushahidi, is part of the network of the COMRADES project. Uchaguzi will provide us their lessons learnt from the active citizen participation in Kenya's elections
10.	TUD	e2MC	Organization Campus Vesta Contact person: Tim van Achte	Started in September 2017	Cross dissemination synergy

Table 13 : List of established collaborations with other projects & initiatives

		Environmentally-sound Land Management based on Data Technologies and Agrobiodiversity, with its strong bottom up approach, aims at raising awareness about the agrobiodiversity domain and addressing major sustainability threats on several layers: ecological, societal, economic, food quality.	.eu/
3.	hackAIR	hackAIR aims to complement official data with community-driven data sources, for collecting, analysing and sharing air quality measurements to community members through low cost open hardware sensors easily assembled by citizens, web and/or mobile phones.	http://www.hackair.eu/
4.	Empatia	Empatia is the first hands-on digital platform for creating and managing a coherent participatory system that integrates multiple channel of citizens' engagement in one simple solution. Empatia mission is to promote inclusion, higher quality deliberation, better voting mechanisms, transparency and accountability in city management.	https://www.empatia-project.eu/
5.	Saving Food	SavingFood offers an innovative and socially responsible solution to the food waste challenge by developing an online networked community of various stakeholders that through collective awareness, knowledge sharing, motivations and incentives, will facilitate the redistribution of surplus food and leftover crops for the benefit of the vulnerable groups of our society.	https://savingfood.eu/
6.	POWER	The project will set up a user-driven Digital Social Platform (DSP) for the expansion and governance of POWER existing water networks.	https://www.power-h2020.eu/

Table 14 : Description of CAPS projects that collaborate with COMRADES

5.4 Direct contact with stakeholders (*face to face meetings*)

5.4.1 List of face to face meetings with stakeholders

S/N	Partner	Name & type of contact	Date of meeting	Venue/Location of the meeting
1.	TUD, Ushahidi	Lt.Gen. Bala Nanda Sharma (Principal of ICMS), Team members	20 Jan. 2017	ICMS
2.	TUD, Ushahidi	Mr. Pradip Koirala (Former joint secretary of disaster management section of Home	21 Jan. 2017	Babarmahal

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		<i>Ministry)</i>		
3.	TUD, Ushahidi	Nepal Army Disaster Management section	22 Jan. 2017	
4.	TUD, Ushahidi	Dr.Prabhu Budhathoki <i>(Member of National Planning Comission)</i>	22 Jan. 2017	Singh Durbar
5.	TUD, Ushahidi	Dr.K.K Tamang <i>(Executive Director of Nepal Armed Police Force Academy)</i>	22 Jan. 2017	Halchowk
6.	TUD, Ushahidi	Mr.Ram Chandra Dhakal <i>(Information and Communication Ministry)</i> and Mr.Anup Nepal <i>(Information & Communication Ministry)</i>	23 Jan. 2017	Singh Durbar
7.	TUD, Ushahidi	Mr.Kush Kumar Joshi <i>(Past President of Federation of Nepalese Chambers of Commerce and Industries)</i>	23 Jan. 2017	Babarmahal
8.	TUD, Ushahidi	Dr.Som Lal Subedi <i>(Chief Secretary of the cabinet)</i>	23 Jan. 2017	Babarmahal
9.	TUD, Ushahidi	Mr. Thule Rai <i>(Senior Superintendent of Nepal Police, Head of Disaster Management Division)</i>	24 Jan. 2017	KTM
10.	TUD, Ushahidi	Dr. Govinda Raj Pokhrel <i>(Chief Executive Officer, Nepal Reconstruction Authority)</i>	24 Jan. 2017	Babarmahal
11.	TUD, Ushahidi	Mr. Prabin Joshi <i>(Communication Expert)</i>	24 Jan. 2017	KTM
12.	TUD, Ushahidi	Retd. Col Ratendra Khatri <i>(World Food Program)</i>	25 Jan. 2017	KTM
13.	TUD, Ushahidi	DSP Sabin Pradhan <i>(Traffic police)</i>	26 Jan. 2017	KTM
14.	TUD, Ushahidi	Mr. Ekraj Niroula <i>(District Development Officer, Kavre)</i>	26 Jan. 2017	Dhulikhel
15.	TUD, Ushahidi	Mr. Shakti Basnet <i>(Former Home Minister)</i>	27 Jan. 2017	KTM

16.	TUD, Ushahidi	Mr. Laxman Upreti, (President, Nepal Forum of Environmental Journalism)	31 Jan. 2017	Lalitpur
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Table 15 : List of face to face meetings with stakeholders

5.4.2 Highlights of face to face meetings with stakeholders

In Panchkhal, several hours drive outside Kathmandu, the field team is recapping the day at the campfire. One of the COMRADES researchers arrived in Nepal just a few hours before and is getting up to speed. In Panchkhal, thanks to the contacts of ICMS, we visited several schools and talked to principals, teachers and students. They elaborated the joint (*community*) decision making processes, the knowledge migration to the cities and the importance of building local knowledge and capacity.

Figure 43 : Face to face meeting with stakeholders in Panchkhal

Figure 44 : Face to face meeting with school principals & teachers in Nepal

Figure 45 : Face to face meeting with the Nepal Army (disaster management section)

Figure 46 : Face to face meeting with professionals of the Institute for Disaster Prevention (Beijing)

5.4.2.1 “Uchaguzi” Deploying COMRADES during the Kenyan Elections

COMRADES was deployed to help monitor the Kenyan elections in what proved to be a tumultuous series of two different elections throughout August and November of 2017. The initiative that made use of the platform is called “Uchaguzi” or, “election” in Swahili. Uchaguzi is an initiative developed in 2008 in partnership between three organisations: Ushahidi, Kenya’s Constitution and Reform Education Consortium (CRECO), and InfoNet, Kenyan NGO.

The Role of the Uchaguzi is to ensure citizen participation in the Kenyan electoral process and access to Electoral Services. Uchaguzi brings together Observers from CRECO: more than 700 monitors located at various polling stations around the country that report on, or verify reports of, issues at polling stations. Uchaguzi included members of Electoral Management Bodies to respond to verified reports and 160 active volunteers who worked around the clock on processing data using the COMRADES platform.

Volunteers were trained in person in Nairobi, or online via web seminars for volunteers who participated from other parts of the world. The mix of governmental partners, local NGOs, and volunteers touched every aspect of the COMRADES project: activists, reporters, and

responders. Reports came in to the platform as: text messages via an established SMS short code (20166); the new Facebook chatbot, detailed in D5.3 “*Second Version of COMRADES platform*”, Twitter, our mobile apps, and directly from web forms.

A complete breakdown of data collected is available in D5.3, but it is worth noting that the platform handled almost twenty thousand messages. Of these, 6,202 contained viable information, which were further verified, combined, or otherwise managed in the platform to result in 1,893 published data points used by responders to react to events as they unfolded.

5.4.2.2 Working with the United Nation’s Humanitarian Data Exchange

COMRADES is excited to announce that it will be working in partnership with the UN’s Humanitarian Data Exchange to ensure that the COMRADES platform can export and import data from and into their website at: <https://data.humdata.org>.

The Humanitarian Data Exchange (*HDX*) is an open platform for sharing data, launched in July 2014. The goal of HDX is to make humanitarian data easy to find and use for analysis. Their growing collection of datasets has been accessed by users in over 200 countries and territories. A team within the [United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs \(OCHA\)](#) manages HDX. OCHA is part of the United Nations Secretariat, responsible for bringing together humanitarian actors to ensure a coherent response to emergencies.

In November 2017, members of Ushahidi and the Technical University of Delft met with the HDX team to discuss moving forward with plans to ensure that the COMRADES platform can integrate with HDX. The collaboration is scheduled to begin in January of 2018.

5.5 Media coverage

5.5.1 List of COMRADES press & media coverage

This list presents all references around COMRADES made in press such as newspapers, newsletters, magazines and so on and third party media such as websites, webpages, blogs, social media (*official accounts*). The types of these items are press releases, articles, interviews, posts etc. The term of “third party media” includes all the communication channels that are not related with either the COMRADES project or the project partners.

<i>S/N</i>	<i>Partner</i>	<i>Type</i> <i>(press release, interview, etc.)</i>	<i>Title</i>	<i>Media</i> <i>(where it was published)</i>	<i>URL</i> <i>(if available)</i>
1.	OU	Press release	Boosts community resilience in disaster events through an A.I. powered platform	Online	https://capssi.eu/caps-tool/comrades-platform/
2.	Ushahidi, TUD	Article	PM bats for reducing disaster risks	The Rising Nepal (<i>newspaper</i>)	http://therisingnepal.org.np/epaper/showimage?img=uploads/epaper/2017-02-02/9bee09ab260851cde5a61733e

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					b33cc2b.jpg
3.	OU	Interview		ChiC project deliverable	n/a
4.	USFD	Radio interview w/ Leon Derczynski	TBA (<i>topic is Fake News</i>)	Bayerischer Rundfunk	n/a
5.	Gov2u	Article	The 2nd COMRADES Newsletter Issue is out!	Joinup platform	https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/news/2nd-comrades-newsletter-i
6.	Gov2u	Post	#Harvey #Remote #volunteer effort. Please #help with update/edit the list:	ICA - International Council for IT in Government Administration Facebook Official Page	https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=1787333111559563&id=100008486736454
7.	Gov2u	Post	7th International Conference on eDemocracy Privacy-Preserving, Secure, Intelligent eGovernment Services	eDemocracy Conference Facebook Official Page	https://www.facebook.com/eDemocracyConference/posts/1147276422044985
8.	Gov2u	Post	The more the merrier! we are thrilled to announce that the COMRADES project has created synergies with hackAIR asset-consumerism.eu EMPATIA Capsella Project (<i>April 26</i>)	CAPSELLA project Facebook page	https://www.facebook.com/capsellaproject/posts/1921386638140315
9.	Gov2u	Post	The more the merrier! we are thrilled to announce that the COMRADES project has created synergies with hackAIR asset-consumerism.eu EMPATIA Capsella	CAPSELLA project Facebook page	https://www.facebook.com/capsellaproject/posts/1946773942268251

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			Project (June 9)		
10.	Gov2u	Post	The more the merrier! we are thrilled to announce that the COMRADES project has created synergies with hackAIR asset-consumerism.eu EMPATIA Capsella Project	Asset-consumerism project Facebook page	https://www.facebook.com/asset-consumerism/posts/1967786656774581
11.	Gov2u	Post	COMRADES is working on a new and exciting collaboration with hackAIR. Keep in mind that both projects are EU Funded, CAPS	hackAIR Facebook page	https://www.facebook.com/hackairproject/posts/299675613809226
12.	Gov2u	Article	COMRADES first field workshops	CAPSSI website	https://capssi.eu/comrades-field-workshop/
13.	Gov2u	Article	The second newsletter of COMRADES is out!	CAPSSI website	https://capssi.eu/comrades-newsletter-2/
14.	Gov2u	Post	Don't miss the 2nd @comradesproject newsletter!	CAPSSI Twitter account	https://twitter.com/CAPSSIEU/status/883314704503984135
15.	Gov2u	Article	Related projects	Asset-consumerism project website	http://www.asset-consumerism.eu/related-projects/
16.	Gov2u	Article	Related projects	hackAIR website	http://www.hackair.eu/related-projects/
17.	Gov2u	Article	CAPS projects	CAPSELLA website	http://www.capsella.eu/caps-projects/

18.		Article	COMRADES	Digital social innovation website	https://digitalsocial.eu/project/1104/%7B%7Bproject.url%7D%7D
19.	Gov2u	Post	Comrades Project Poster NOW available on issuu.com	Centre for Integrated Emergency Management Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/CIEMUiA/posts/1939205509430601
20.	Gov2u	Post	Comrades Project Poster NOW available on issuu.com	CAPSSI EU Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/capssi.eu/posts/821991674672563

Table 16 : List of COMRADES press & media coverage

5.5.2 List of COMRADES references at partners' communication channels

This list presents all the references around the COMRADES in partners' communication channels (*websites, press releases, newsletters and other media e.g. partners' social media official accounts*)

S/N	Partner	Type (press release, interview, etc.)	Title	Media (where it was published)	URL (if available)
1.	OU	Press release	COMRADES sails through its mid-term review	Online	http://kmi.open.ac.uk/news/18925
2.	Gov2u	Post	#Harvey #Remote #volunteer effort. Please #help with update/edit the list:	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10155698517616057
3.	Gov2u	Post	The 2nd Comrades #Newsletter Issue featured on #Joinup!!	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10155571951981057
4.	Gov2u	Post	The second Comrades newsletter issue is featured on Capssi EU!!	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10155515903771057
	Gov2u	Post	The second	Gov2u	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10155515903771057

5.			newsletter issue of the Comrades is out!	Facebook Page	.com/Gov2u/posts/10155479266971057
6.	Gov2u	Post	Comrades #Project #Meeting in the #Hague	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10155473796916057
7.	Gov2u	Article	Projects	Gov2u website	http://www.gov2u.org/index.php/learn
8.	TUD	Article	My involvement in the COMRADES research project	Universitetet i Agder website	https://www.uia.no/studenter-i-forskningsprosjekt/my-involvement-in-the-comrades-research-project2
9.	TUD	Article	Information can help to save lives	Universitetet i Agder website	https://www.uia.no/en/news/information-can-help-to-save-lives
10.	USFD	Article	Current Grant Portofolio	The University of Sheffield website	https://www.sheffield.ac.uk/dcs/research/currentgrantsportfolio
11.	Gov2u	Post	The public deliverable of our project "D2.1 Requirements for boosting..	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10155946537396057

Table 17 : List of COMRADES references at partners' communication channels

5.5.3 Highlights of COMRADES press & media coverage

The "Rising Nepal" newspaper published an article that was referred to the EU funded CAPS (*Collective Awareness Platforms for Sustainability and Social Innovation for Making Crisis Resilient Community*) workshops which took place in Nepal. It featured a statement of the Nepalese Prime minister who attended the workshop and expressed his readiness to promote and implement risk reduction actions, as mentioned in the Sendai framework.

EC ready to hold polls: Yadav

RSS
Phalebas (Parbat), Feb 1
Chief Election Commissioner (CEC) Dr Ayodhi Prasad Yadav has said the Election Commission was ready for conducting any sorts of election.

Speaking at the foundation stone laying ceremony of a new building of the District Election Office, Parbat this morning, the CEC said the Commission was in touch with the government regarding the issue of announcing the poll date with no further delay. Stating that the date for any election should be announced before 100 days of the election date, he called on the government to declare the poll date by formulating necessary laws soon.

It was the responsibility of us all to create a ground for holding the election in a free, fair and neutral atmosphere.

PM bats for reducing disaster risks

By A Staff Reporter
Kathmandu, Feb. 1

Prime Minister Pushpa Kamal Dahal Prachanda's Wednesday said that the government was serious about reducing disaster.

Addressing an international workshop on 'Collective Awareness Platforms for Sustainability and Social Innovation for Making Crisis Resilient Community' in the capital, Prime Minister Prachanda said that the government was ready to learn from the past, preserve institutional memory and utilise that memory for the benefit of posterity.

"With a longer term vision of disaster risk reduction and preparedness in mind, the government is fully committed to the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction and its four priorities

and seven targets," the PM said.

"We want to build institutions, strengthen the existing ones, and streamline the legal and institutional frameworks for building resilience and preparedness as envisioned by the Sendai Framework."

He said that the government was fully aware that sustained local, national, regional and international efforts with adequate resource backing are essential to realise those international commitments as outlined in the Sendai framework.

Stating that it was important for Nepal because of the unique geography and fragility of mountain ecosystem, he said that the natural disasters such as earthquake, flash floods, landslides, forest fire and melting and outburst of glacial lakes have increased the vulnerability and

endangered lives and livelihoods of the people in Nepal.

Lauding the role played by the government, people, community, civil society and non-governmental partners during the recent earthquake, the PM said that the workshop was a useful and important platform to raise collective awareness and share experiences and best practices for building resilient communities.

He said that the impact of the natural disasters could be reduced with collective efforts and make people better prepared to cope with the unforeseen eventualities.

Stating that every major disaster teaches invaluable lesson of how to survive such crises and helps innovate ways and means to be resilient and this probably was

See Page 6

Figure 47 : Press coverage of the COMRADES conference in Nepal – The Rising Nepal newspaper

5.6 Publications

S/N	WP	Date of publication	Title of publication	Partner & Authors	Type (workshop, journal, conference, demo, etc.)	Title of the periodical or series	Open Access (Y/N)
1.	4	Oct. 2017	Semantic Wide and Deep Learning for Detecting Crisis - Information Categories on Social Media	OU: <i>Burel, Gregoire; Saif, Hassan and Alani, Harith</i>	Conf paper	ISWC proceedings	Yes
2.	3, 4	2017	Pro-Environmental Campaigns via Social Media: Analysing Awareness and Behaviour Patterns. Journal of Web Science	OU: <i>Miriam Fernandez, Lara Piccolo, Harith Alani</i> USFD: <i>Diana Maynard</i>	Journal paper	The Journal of Web Science	Yes
3.	4	Oct. 2017	Statistical Semantic Classification	OU: <i>Prashant Khare,</i>	Workshop paper	Hybrid Statistical Semantic	Yes

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			of Crisis Information	<i>Miriam Fernandez, Harith Alani</i>		Understanding and Emerging Semantics (<i>HSSUES</i>), 16th ISWC	
4.	4	Sept. 2017	An analysis of UK Policing Engagement via Social Media	OU: <i>Miriam Fernandez, Harith Alani</i>	Conf. paper	Social Informatics. (<i>SocInfo</i>)	Yes
5.	3	Sept 2017	Results of the WNUT2017 Shared Task on Novel and Emerging Entity Recognition	USFD: <i>L Derczynski, E. Nichols, M van Erp, N. Limsopatham</i>	Workshop paper	Proceedings of the 3rd Workshop on Noisy, User-generated Text (<i>W-NUT</i>), EMNLP	Yes
6.	3	Sept. 2017	Simple Open Stance Classification for Rumour Analysis	USFD: <i>A Aker, L Derczynski, K Bontcheva</i>	Conf. paper	Proceedings of the conference on Recent Advances in Natural Language Processing	Yes
7.	3	Aug. 2017	SemEval-2017 Task 8: RumourEval: Determining rumour veracity and support for rumours	USFD: <i>Leon Derczynski, Kalina Bontcheva, Maria Liakata, Rob Procter, Geraldine Wong Sak Hoi, Arkaitz Zubiaga</i>	Workshop paper	Proceedings of the workshop on Semantic Evaluation (<i>SemEval</i>), ACL	Yes
8.	3	Sept. 2017	Proceedings of the 3rd Workshop on Noisy User-generated Text	USFD: <i>L Derczynski, W Xu, A Ritter, T Baldwin</i>		3rd Workshop on Noisy User-generated Text	Yes

9.	3	May 2017	I Augenstein, L Derczynski, K Bontcheva	USFD: <i>I Augenstein, L Derczynski, K Bontcheva</i>		Computer Speech & Language	Yes
10	3	Mar. 2018	Rumour verification using stance only	USFD: <i>Sebastian Dungs, Ahmet Aker, Kalina Bontcheva, Norbert Fuhr</i>		ECIR 2018	
11.	3	Sept. 2017	An Extensible Multilingual Open Source Lemmatizer	USFD: <i>Ahmet Aker, Firas Sabbah, Johann Petrak</i>		RANLP 2017	
12.	3	-	Investigating the power of crowd wisdom for rumour verification	USFD: <i>Sebastian Dungs, Ahmet Aker, Arkaitz Zubiaga, Kalina Bontcheva, Norbert Fuhr</i>		JASIST Journal	
13	2	Dec. 2017	Making sense of crises: the implications of information asymmetries for resilience and social justice in disaster-ridden communities	TU Delft <i>Tina Comes, Kenny Meesters</i> UiA <i>Stina Torjesen</i>	Journal paper	Sustainable and Resilient Infrastructure, 2017	Yes

Table 18 : List of COMRADES publications in Y2

6 Overview of WP6 activities in Y2 & Upcoming Actions in Y3

6.1 Overview of WP6 activities in Y2

The current section provides an overview of the communication and dissemination tools and activities used and respectively performed from the January 2017 to December 2017 (Y2). **Table 19** briefly provides all the information presented in previous sections of the current document.

<i>Type of Tool or Activity</i>	<i>Measurement Unit</i>	<i>Number</i>
COMRADES website	Pageviews	17,443
	Sessions (<i>visits</i>)	2,337
	Users (<i>unique visitors</i>)	1,482
Social media	Facebook page likes	138
	Twitter followers	309
	LinkedIn connections	123
Digital Publishing Platforms	Items uploaded at Scribd	22
	Items uploaded at Issuu	22
	Items uploaded at SlideShare	250
Newsletter	Newsletter Issues	1
Promotional materials	New promotional material designed	1
Outreach activities	Events organized	14
Press & Media coverage	References in press & media	20
Third party events	Participated & presented the project in third party events	13
Collaboration with other projects	Established collaborations with EU funded projects & other initiatives (<i>CAPS project included</i>)	10
	Established collaborations with CAPS projects	6
Publications	Number of publications	13

Table 19 : Overview of WP6 activities in Y2

6.2 Upcoming Actions in Y3

The period *January 2018 – December 2018* will cover the third year of COMRADES lifecycle. A brief description of the actions that will be undertaken are showed at the subsections that follow.

6.2.1 COMRADES website

The COMRADES website will continue to serve as the key online communication tool of the project and for this reason it will be updated with:

- project news in regular basis;
- events related to the project's topic;
- stories and news from CAPs projects (*synergies established*);
- project's outcomes such as a presented papers;
- design improvements;
- COMRADES profiles of digital publishing platforms will be embedded

6.2.2 COMRADES social media

The social media of the project are significant tools for attracting more audience to the project's website and convey the project's messages from one source to many recipients. Therefore the posts will be about:

- project news (*accompanied with links from the COMRADES website*);
- events related to the project's topic;
- news from CAPs projects and/or repost them (*synergies established*);
- project's outcomes (*accompanied with links from the COMRADES website*);
- COMRADES profiles in digital publishing platforms and their uploaded items (*project's results*);

Overall, the effort in social media will be focused on expanding the networking in order to broaden the community of interest around the COMRADES.

6.2.3 Newsletter issue No.3

As already mentioned in **chapter 4.2**, the newsletter is a communication tool that assists WP6 in reaching the target groups and conveying to them the major COMRADES developments with main aim to attract their attention and engage them.

For avoiding "spamming" the recipients of the project's e-newsletter the next issue will be published in June 2018 and will also ensure that the project's results will be communicated. Nevertheless, the possibility of creating and distributing more than one newsletter issue during Y3 cannot be excluded in case of unanimous consortium's decision for an extra one (*or more*). This possibility will be further discussed in the next project meeting under the framework of the coordinated actions for exploiting the project and its outcomes.

6.2.4 Press releases

The press release is a formal announcement of the project to the European and international press. Press releases are issued to announce important news and achievements, as well as workshops and events organized by project partners. For Y3 this communication tool will be used by an intensified manner.

6.2.5 Promotional materials

The marketing collaterals created so far will be further updated as the project enters into the third phase of the dissemination process. During this final phase, supplementary with the rest of the communication activities (*presentations in third party events, other outreach activities, face to face meetings with stakeholders and so on*), the project's results will be communicated via the COMRADES promotional material in order to ensure their widespread transmission to target groups and/or potential future customers of the COMRADES solution.

6.2.6 Collaboration with CAPS projects

In Y2, the dissemination and communication team of COMRADES sent invitations for collaboration to 18 CAPS projects where 6 of them responded. For Y3, an attempt for re-approaching these CAPS projects that have not responded will be made without neglecting establishing new ones. The initiative of CAPPsi to organize regular teleconferences among CAPS projects will reinforce cross dissemination synergies with them.

Concerning the collaborations that have been already established, attendance from COMRADES partners to workshops and events organized by these projects and vice versa will be made (*CAPS projects events cross attendance*).

6.2.7 Participation in events

In the context of promoting the findings in stakeholders as well as in potential future customers of the COMRADES solution the consortium will make targeted actions for events participation.

7 Conclusions

This document constitutes an annual report on the communication and dissemination activities made by the COMRADES consortium within the period January 2017 – December 2017 (Y2). Additionally, the communication tools that were used under the same period, the actions related with them and their performance is also presented.

The effectiveness of the communication tools was measured continuously throughout Y2 and their results were evaluated by the communication and dissemination team of the COMRADES project.

The second year was a very productive year from dissemination's perspective as many papers were published and communicated to target groups, outcomes were presented in third party events and a successful COMRADES conference in Nepal was organized. This conference was embraced by the local press and attended by activists, members of the civil protection, civilians and many members of the Nepalese government included the Prime Minister.

Summarizing, we used a mixture of tools and activities in order to achieve the WP6 objectives of Y2 and be prepared for the third phase of dissemination. The activities that will follow in the upcoming period will be made in respect of exploiting the COMRADES results after the end of EU funding.

The current deliverable was submitted in December 2017 (M24) as foreseen in the DoA.

APPENDIX I – Google Analytics

The most important data related to the website can be found in the figures below.

Figure 48 : Audience overview – Google analytics

Country	Sessions	% Sessions
1. Greece	538	23.02%
2. United States	366	15.66%
3. United Kingdom	293	12.54%
4. Netherlands	167	7.15%
5. Norway	110	4.71%
6. Italy	99	4.24%
7. Spain	86	3.68%
8. Belgium	63	2.70%
9. China	48	2.05%
10. Germany	45	1.93%

Figure 49 : Countries (Top 10) – Google analytics

Browser	Sessions	% Sessions
1. Chrome	1,415	60.55%
2. Firefox	365	15.62%
3. Mozilla Compatible Agent	218	9.33%
4. Safari	202	8.64%
5. Internet Explorer	69	2.95%
6. Edge	25	1.07%
7. Android Webview	16	0.68%
8. Safari (in-app)	11	0.47%
9. Opera Mini	6	0.26%
10. Opera	3	0.13%

Figure 50 : Browsers (Top 10) – Google analytics

APPENDIX II – Promotional Materials (screenshots)

Figure 51 : COMRADES poster

Figure 52 : COMRADES brochure - updated

At a glance

Response to crisis often reveals organisational and technological shortcomings, which threaten community recovery. It is imperative to develop human-centred technologies that take into account actual real world practices of affected populations and responders.

COMRADES aims to empower communities with intelligent socio-technical solutions to help them reconnect, respond to, and recover from crisis situations.

Project started

 1 January 2016
 and will last 3 years.

Goals of COMRADES

- **Community Resilience**
Providing intelligent Information and Communication technologies to boost community resilience, by increasing the ability of a community to take collective actions, and to utilise available resources to self-organise and respond to crises.
- **Community Engagement**
Platform will be designed and created bottom-up by communities. Project will run several co-design and engagement events with communities, along with theoretical research.
- **Informativeness of Citizen Reports**
During crises, a very large number of messages are often posted on various social media platforms by using the hashtags dedicated to the crises at hand. COMRADES will produce a set of automatic filters, to efficiently and intelligently identify the messages of sufficient relevance and value.
- **Content and Source Validity Assessment**
Falsified crises and emergency reports are amongst the biggest concerns of humanitarians and communities towards using social media content during crisis. COMRADES will develop methods to help responders with assessing the validity of content and its source and also provide responders with means for alerting the community through the COMRADES platform and social media of unreliable content and information sources currently circulating.
- **Emergency Events**
COMRADES aims to develop tools and algorithms for automatically and accurately detecting, modelling, and matchmaking emergency events.
- **Participatory community innovation during crises**
 - The services and platform will be open source using open and linked data, thus facilitating the extension of the platform to other application areas.
 - The COMRADES platform will be accessible over the Web and mobile devices.

Active citizen participation

- The platform will encourage community-wide participation, by enabling local (communities in crisis zones) and remote (digital activists and responders) individuals and communities to come together and share knowledge through their crises reports (community reporters), to produce and access filtered and quality collective information, and to be connected with others based on emergency needs and offers.
- COMRADES will involve citizens at two levels:
 - By engaging multiple communities in the requirements, design, and evaluation tasks and
 - By producing a platform to be primarily used by the citizens, to help their communities and fellow citizens. The platform will be based on Ushahidi; a common platform for crises mapping, developed in collaboration with iHub.

Communities

COMRADES will engage with three types of specific communities that are core to effective resilience efforts:

- **Activists (platform deployers):** individuals and groups of people who set up instances of the Ushahidi platform.
- **Responders:** communities that organise and coordinate resources and provide expertise when the Ushahidi platform is deployed.
- **Reporters:** communities who report on crisis.

Project website: www.comrades-project.eu
 Contact email: communication@comrades-project.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 647847

Figure 53 : COMRADES factsheet - updated

APPENDIX III – Newsletter Issue No.2 (screenshots)

The following figures consist screenshots of each section of the second COMRADES e-newsletter issue that was published in June 2017. It is available online at its original version on section “Press Kit”, subsection “[Newsletter](#)”.

myor cannot read a lr email, please click [here](#)

COMRADES
Newsletter Issue No.2 – June 2017

© COMRADES Project

Figure: The community of Laharepauwa, Nepal presenting their information timeline post 2015 earthquake

COMRADES Workshops in Nepal

From the 18th of January to the 2nd of February 2017 the COMRADES project in close collaboration with Institute of Crisis Management Studies (ICMS) of Tribhuvan University (Nepal) completed a series of highly successful international workshops. Over the course of 16 days, workshops, focus group sessions, lectures, and interviews with approximately 150 people in Kathmandu and in remote areas of Nepal were conducted.

[READ MORE](#)

Stories

Empowering Local Communities

The COMRADES project has reached out at local level to engage communities but to also gather feedback that will enable a better user experience with a more User Centric approach.

We'd like to share some of our stories!

Workshops in Rasuwa, Nepal

[READ THE STORY](#)

COMRADES / ICMS symposium

[READ THE STORY](#)

Field team briefing

[READ THE STORY](#)

International contacts

[READ THE STORY](#)

Joint design in practice

[WATCH THE VIDEO](#)

Opinions

Information can help to save lives

by Alle Christiansen

The Nepalese Prime Minister joins UIA research workshops on supporting communities with information in crisis.

Workshops are about exchanging knowledge and experience. We learn from the participants, but at the same time we hope to bring new insights to them. So, you could say that the scientists learnt as much as the participants in the workshops," says Kenny Meesters, scientist at UIA's Centre for Integrated Emergency Management (CIEM) and coordinator of the workshops in Nepal. Source: [University of Aagder](#)

My involvement in the COMRADES research project

by Daniel Petersen

A few months ago, I wouldn't have seen myself involved in a research project at the University of Agder, much less a Horizon-2020 EU-project where the student assistant position at UIA was meant for master candidates. As a bachelor candidate for IT and information systems it is first and foremost an honor to partake in a project of such magnitude and most importantly, value; value because of the humanitarian aspect of an otherwise highly technical project. Source: [University of Aagder](#)

Events & Conferences

The COMRADES project team has found some events you may find interesting!

[Why don't you take a look?](#)

Other Project News

The Rising Nepal says

The "Rising Nepal" newspaper published an article that made a reference to the EU funded CAPS (Collective Awareness Platforms for Sustainability and Social Innovation for Making Crisis Resilient Community) workshops which took place in Nepal.

Moreover, the Prime Minister attended the workshop and expressed his readiness to promote and implement risk reduction actions, as mentioned in the sendal framework. You can read the full article [here](#).

COMRADES announces brand new Collaborations

The COMRADES team is thrilled to announce its latest collaborations with four different EU funded projects. All of the projects are part of the CAPS initiative (Collective Awareness Platforms for Sustainability and Social Innovation) and aim to create awareness of emerging sustainability challenges and of the role that each and every one of us can play to ease them through collective action.

[Read More](#)

Member of the COMRADES consortium present paper "Presentation of DoRES – A Three-tier Ontology for Modelling Crises in the Digital Age"

The paper's main theme concerned the importance of collecting, organizing, analyzing and sharing critical information during emergency crises. That was the concept behind the creation of the DoRES ontology.

[Read More](#)

Project Meeting in the Hague

The COMRADES consortium gathered at The Hague for a two day meeting to discuss their most recent research and results, and to set work plans for the next few months. In this meeting, the consortium focused their attention on analysing the requirements gathered from the workshops in Nepal, and how these requirements can be catered for by the various partners and workpackages in the project.

Photo credit: Dorte Petersen